

ELASTOPLASTIC ANALYSIS OF THERMAL STRESSES AND AXIAL LOADING IN FIBER REINFORCED METALS

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An analytical model has been developed for the elastoplastic analysis of unidirectional fiber composites. The large triaxial residual stress state resulting from the differences in thermal expansion coefficients between the composite constituents was predicted. Thermal fatigue problems in tungsten wire reinforced metals were analysed and different matrix materials were discussed in this respect. The residual stress states in the reaction layers between fiber and matrix were also calculated. The response of composites subjected to axial loading when the composites contain residual stresses from the fabrication process was predicted and compared to tensile tests.

The results show that the residual stresses appearing in a tungsten wire reinforced metal subjected to a temperature cycle are of great importance. The thermal fatigue lives of potential matrices are considerable reduced by these stresses. Preliminary fatigue tests confirm these results.

In reaction layers the stresses are of such magnitude that microcracks are estimated. Analysis of heat treated composites indicate such cracks along the wires.

INTRODUCTION

Metal matrix composites consisting of refractory metal wires in a high temperature alloy matrix are attractive for applications at elevated temperature. Thus, tungsten wire reinforced superalloys have demonstrated a very good resistance to creep and stress rupture. An introduction of such composites in blades and vanes in advanced gas turbines allow for a considerable increase in the turbine inlet gas temperature and a reduction of the blade cooling requirement.

However, the fiber reinforced metals have a complicated structure and the internal stresses must be analysed to characterize the material. A stiff fiber is combined with a ductile matrix and often a brittle reaction layer is formed between the fiber and the matrix. A thin diffusion barrier coating of, for instance, hafnium carbide or hafnium nitride, is often used to prevent fiber/matrix interaction. The differences in the coefficients of thermal expansion of the constituents give rise to a large triaxial stress state with plastic deformations, at least in the matrix material.

The macroscopic thermo-mechanical properties of unidirectional composites can be predicted by approximate methods, which do not take into account the detailed geometry of the microstructure, [1]. However, many aspects of the composite behaviour can be studied only on the microscale. Fatigue and fracture as well as the behaviour of the reaction layer are among the phenomena which are controlled by micro-mechanical processes. Some such analyses have been described in the literature. Hoffman made a simple estimation of the thermal stresses based on a cylinder model and the theory for a thick walled cylinder [2]. A similar model have been used by Dvorak and Rao [3], but they discussed the plastic deformations in more detail. A finite element method has been used by Dvorak, Rao and Tarn to predict the composite stresses on a microscale [4]. They have also investigated the composite initial yield surface in relation to micro-yielding for the boron-aluminum system. Hecker et al have used a cylinder model to study the mechanical interaction in a composite subjected to temperature changes or axial loading [5]. Due to the volume fraction fibers the cylinder core can either represent the fiber or the matrix. The core in their model is divided into a number of concentric cylinders.

In the present work the microstresses were analyzed in tungsten wire reinforced metals subjected to thermal cycling and external axial loading. A model was introduced where both elastic and plastic deformations were taken into account. Special attention was paid to thermal fatigue problems and stresses in the reaction layers.

ANALYTICAL COMPOSITE MODEL

The type of composites considered represents a complicated group of material systems, where rigid fibers are surrounded by brittle reaction layers in a ductile matrix. An analysis of such a material involves the prediction of internal stresses when the composite is subjected to external loading and thermal cycling within a wide temperature range. It was considered suitable to use a cylindrical model of the material, which is rather simple handle mathematically.

Thus, the composite was modelled by a cylinder where the core represented the fiber and the reaction zone as well as the matrix were represented by the cylinder case. The case was divided in a number of concentric cylinders of varying thicknesses and different material properties. The composite model is illustrated in Fig. 1.

The fibers in an unidirectional composite can be in a hexagonal or quadratic array, but in a real composite the fibers are more or less irregularly distributed. The cylinder model has more accuracy the less the fiber content, and is more adequate for a hexagonal array than for a quadratic one.

Fig. 1. Composite model.

The external radius of the model was taken to be

$$R_y = \left[(R_{rz} + H)^2 / (V_f + V_{rz}) \right]^{1/2} \quad (1)$$

where R_{rz} = outer radius of the reaction zone; H = thickness of the reaction zone; V_f = fiber volume fraction; V_{rz} = reaction material volume fraction.

The assumptions for the model can be summed up as follow.

1. The constituents are perfectly bonded to each other.
2. Each constituent is homogeneous and isotropic.
3. End effects are neglected.
4. There is no stress interaction between neighboring composite cylinders.

First, a general elastic solution was developed for the composite subjected to axial and thermal loading and then the solution was expanded to the plastic region.

Let us consider one of the components in the model, a hollow cylinder. Only that part of the cylinder which is a sufficient distance from the ends will be considered. Then, it may be assumed that plane sections perpendicular to the axis remain plane and perpendicular. The cylindrical system, r, θ, z , defines the principal axis at all points in the cylinder. The elastic theory for a thick-walled cylinder gives the following equations
Radial force equilibrium:

$$\frac{d\sigma_r}{dr} + \frac{\sigma_r}{r} - \frac{\sigma_\theta}{r} = 0 \quad (2)$$

The compatibility equations express the strains in terms of the displacement:

$$\epsilon_r = \frac{du}{dr} \quad (3)$$

$$\epsilon_\theta = \frac{u}{r} \quad (4)$$

where u is the radial displacement. The axial strain, ϵ_z , is prescribed when the composite is subjected to axial loading. In the case when the composite is subjected to a temperature change ϵ_z is given by the connection to neighboring cylinders.

The stresses can be expressed in terms of strains and thermal expansion as:

$$\sigma_r = K \left[(1-\nu)\epsilon_r + \nu\epsilon_\theta + \nu\epsilon_z - (1+\nu)\alpha T \right] \quad (5)$$

$$\sigma_\theta = K \left[(1-\nu)\epsilon_\theta + \nu\epsilon_r + \nu\epsilon_z - (1+\nu)\alpha T \right] \quad (6)$$

$$\sigma_z = K \left[(1-\nu)\epsilon_z + \nu\epsilon_r + \nu\epsilon_\theta - (1+\nu)\alpha T \right] \quad (7)$$

where

$$K = E/(1+\nu)(1-2\nu)$$

A combination of eq:s (2) to (7) gives the following differential equation for radial displacements:

$$\frac{d^2u}{dr^2} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{du}{dr} - \frac{u}{r^2} = 0 \quad (8)$$

For the i :th cylinder in the composite model the solution is:

$$u_i = C_1^i r + C_2^i / r \quad (9)$$

Let us assume that the composite model consists of the core and N cylinder components. Then $2N + 2$ boundary conditions are necessary to determine the constants in eq. (9) for all components. These conditions can be derived from the following requirements:

1. The radial displacements must be continuous at all component interfaces.
2. The radial stress component must also be continuous at all interfaces.
3. At the center of the core the displacement must be finite.
4. We also need a condition for the outside surface of the model. The most convenient approximation is to require the radial stress component, σ_r , to be zero. This condition is more adequate the less fiber content the composite contains.

These conditions give $2N + 2$ equations and the $2N + 2$ constants C_1^i and C_2^i ($i = 0, 1, \dots, N$) can be solved. When an axial loading is applied to the composite at a constant temperature ϵ_z is prescribed as a driving force and the thermal expansion therm, αT , is zero. In the other situation to be considered the composite is subjected to a temperature change and the differences in thermal expansion coefficients are the driving force for the internal stresses. Then, ϵ_z is unknown and an additional boundary condition is needed. Therefore the following equation of equilibrium for the forces in the axial direction is introduced:

$$\int_0^{R_y} \sigma_z r dr = 0 \quad (10)$$

where R_y = outer radius of the composite model.

The analysis of a composite containing at least two different strain hardening materials subjected to multiaxial states of stress in the elastoplastic region is a very complex problem. Here, a method, based on equations developed by Hecker et

al [6], was utilized. Constitutive relations for the total strain increments (elastic plus plastic) were introduced by the following set of equations:

$$\begin{aligned} d\epsilon_z &= \frac{1}{P} \left[d\sigma_z - m(d\sigma_\theta + d\sigma_r) \right] \\ d\epsilon_\theta &= \frac{1}{P} \left[d\sigma_\theta - m(d\sigma_z + d\sigma_r) \right] \\ d\epsilon_r &= \frac{1}{P} \left[d\sigma_r - m(d\sigma_z + d\sigma_\theta) \right] \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

where P and m are material parameters. These stress-strain relations are physically correct only for proportional loading, that is, if the ratios of the principal stresses remain constant [7]. The accuracy of any analysis, where the loading is not of the proportional type, will be a function of the actual deviation from a proportional loading path.

It is apparent that these relations are of the same form as Hooke's equations for elastic behaviour, with P replacing the elastic modulus, E, and m replacing Poisson's ratio, ν . The discussed elastic solution of the composite analysis can therefore be used also for the plasticity problem.

In order to comply with the proposed constitutive relations, Eq.(11), it is necessary to define an effective strain which is based on the total strain increments. For this purpose the following equation, which relates the total effective strain increment, $d\bar{\epsilon}$, to the total strain increments, was introduced:

$$d\bar{\epsilon} = \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2(1+m)} \left[(d\epsilon_z - d\epsilon_\theta)^2 + (d\epsilon_\theta - d\epsilon_r)^2 + (d\epsilon_r - d\epsilon_z)^2 \right]^{0.5} \quad (12)$$

P and m, the two material parameters introduced are determined from the effective stress-strain curve of the material. P is defined as the instantaneous tangent modulus of the effective stress-strain curve. It can be expressed as:

$$P = d\bar{\sigma}/d\bar{\epsilon} \quad (13)$$

In the elastic region, P is equal to the elastic modulus E, and, in the plastic region, P decreases according to the strain hardening.

The parameter m represents an effective Poisson's ratio and can be determined by assuming the separation of the total strain into elastic and plastic components. Assuming constancy of volume for the completely plastic strain increment, m can be given as

$$m = 0.5 - (0.5-\nu) \frac{d\epsilon^e}{d\bar{\epsilon}} \quad (14)$$

where $d\epsilon^e$ denotes the elastic portion of the total strain increment.

The effective stress $\bar{\sigma}$ can be determined by the relation $d\bar{\sigma} = f(d\bar{\epsilon})$ from a uniaxial tensile test curve. The postulate of isotropic hardening was utilized to specify the change of yield condition with plastic deformations. This implies that the yield surface expands in size without any change in shape, which from a physical viewpoint predicts a negative Bauschinger effect.

It is of great importance to take the temperature dependence of the material properties into consideration. The developed calculation program allows for variations in both physical and mechanical properties of the composite constituents.

The numerical analysis of a composite subjected to temperature cycles or axial loading is outlined below.

Step 1. Application of a load increment, either ΔT or $\Delta\epsilon_z$

- Step 2. Estimation of an effective strain increment, $d\bar{\epsilon}$, for each cylinder. The applied load increment may indicate loading or unloading, which are treated in different ways in the program. The estimated $d\bar{\epsilon}$ is added to the accumulative effective strain $\bar{\epsilon}$.
- Step 3. Determination of the material parameters P and m for the estimated $\bar{\epsilon}$ from the stress-strain curve corresponding to the actual temperature. Unloading is then considered to occur by elastic deformations.
- Step 4. Calculation of increments in stress and strain components for all cylinders by solving the system of equations described previously.
- Step 5. Determination of a new effective strain increment $d\bar{\epsilon}$ from Eq.(12). This strain increment is compared to that estimated in step 2. Then the program return to step 2 for estimation of a new $d\bar{\epsilon}$ and the iteration is continued until satisfactory convergence is reached.

EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

Composite specimens were prepared by a new method based on hot isostatic pressing (HIP) [8]. The reinforcement was a tungsten wire containing 2 wt % ThO₂ with a diameter of 0.3 mm. Two types of matrices were used: Stainless steel AISI type 304 and Kovar (Fe; 29 Ni; 17 Co). The composites were fabricated at a temperature of about 1100°C for 3 hours. A reaction layer was found to form between wire and matrix during the HIP-process.

The short-term tensile behaviour of the composites was studied in air using standard testing equipment [9]. The composite thermal expansion behaviour was examined by dilatometer tests [1].

For the calculation of internal composite stresses the mechanical and physical data of the composite constituents are needed. Hence, the tensile properties of the uncombined tungsten wires and matrix materials were obtained with a standard testing machine. Physical data were taken from material handbooks.

Test materials with the composition of the reaction layer were produced by a HIP-process of powder. The thermal expansion coefficient was measured by dilatometer tests. Young's modulus was estimated from compressive tests of the material.

Preliminary thermal fatigue tests of composites were carried out in an equipment, specially design for composite tests.

RESIDUAL STRESSES

To illustrate the present theory we will first consider a tungsten wire (W-2% ThO₂) reinforced stainless steel (type 304) composite and predict the appearing residual stresses after the composite fabrication. The mechanical properties of the constituents were obtained of material, heat treated to simulate the fabrication process. Fig. 2 shows the stress-strain relations of the tungsten (W) and stainless steel (SS) used in the calculations. The differences in thermal expansion coefficients between tungsten and potential matrices shown in Fig. 3, are the driving forces to cause internal thermal stresses.

The elastic constants were selected from Table 1.

Table 1

Material	E [GPa]				ν			
	20°C	300°C	600°C	900°C	20°C	380°C	600°C	900°C
W-2% ThO ₂	400	388	377	363	0.17	0.17	0.17	0.17
SS Type 304	210	195	178	158	0.27	0.29	0.31	0.25
Kovar	190	175	160	145	0.29	0.30	0.30	0.29

Fig. 2. Experimental stress-strain curves for stainless steel, type 304 and W-2% ThO₂ wires.

Fig. 3. Thermal expansion coefficients for W-2% ThO₂ wires, stainless steel and Kovar.

The composites were fabricated at 1100°C and then cooled to room temperature. Above a certain temperature, almost all internal stresses were relaxed by matrix creep. Thus, the composite was assumed to be stress-free at 900°C. During cooling the internal stresses increase continuously because the matrix contracts faster than does the reinforcement. Fig. 4 shows the calculated effective microstresses in the fiber and the matrix close to the interface as a function of temperature for the cooling from fabrication followed by heating to 700°C. The hysteresis effect during the temperature cycling is due to plastic deformations in the matrix.

After fabrication the composites contain a considerable amount of residual stresses. The distributions of the stress components at room temperature in composites with different fiber contents are presented in Fig. 5. The axial stress component in the fibers is very dependent on volume fraction fibers, and when the composite contains too few reinforcements the fiber stress can reach a catastrophic level. Since the matrix has been deformed plastically during cooling the variation in the residual stress-components due to the fiber content is limited.

Axial thermal expansion of composites have been calculated with the program. While the tungsten wires were deformed elastically in the present example the composite thermal expansion coefficient parallel to the fibers (z-direction) was defined at temperature T as

Fig. 4. Predicted effective stresses in fiber and matrix as a function of temperature. $V_f = 0.40$.

Fig. 5. Theoretical predicted residual stresses in a tungsten wire reinforced stainless steel, after fabrication.

$$\frac{d\epsilon_{cz}}{dT} = \frac{\Delta\epsilon_{cz}}{\Delta T} = \frac{\alpha_f \Delta T - \Delta\sigma_{fz}/E_f}{\Delta T} \quad (15)$$

An example of the coefficient as a function of temperature for a stainless steel containing 40 % tungsten wires is shown in Fig. 6. In the figure the coefficients

Fig. 6. Predicted thermal expansion coefficients in a tungsten/stainless steel composite. $V_f = 0.40$.

for uncombined matrix and reinforcement materials are also shown. It is evident that a temperature cycle results in the formation of a hysteresis loop and that the composite thermal expansion behaviour is quite distinct from that of the constituents. The residual stresses from the composite fabrication were taken into consideration in the calculation. The hysteresis effect is consistent with the predicted internal stresses and is a consequence of the plastic deformations in the matrix. The more stiffness is shown by a constituent the more it influences on the composite thermal expansion. In our example, where the matrix was very weak compared to the tungsten wires, the coefficient was close to that of tungsten.

Thermal expansion of composites was measured by a dilatometer. The predicted coefficients were in fair agreement with those measured even if an exact comparison was difficult due to uncertainty in the estimation of residual stresses in composites after fabrication and specimen preparation.

THERMAL FATIGUE

The internal stresses in a tungsten wire reinforced metal subjected to temperature cycling are of such magnitude that thermal fatigue is an important obstacle to their introduction as a turbine blade material. The appearing internal stresses are due mainly to the thermal expansion effect but phase transformations can also influence the response of the composite to thermal cycling. In order to minimize the thermal fatigue problems in the matrix it is important to make a proper selection of material combinations. Therefore, thermal stresses in the matrix for some potential composite systems were predicted and compared to their thermal fatigue resistance.

As an example, Fig. 7 shows the predicted effective stress-strain relation in the matrix, close to the fiber/matrix interface, in a Hastelloy X containing 40 vol-% tungsten wires. The composite was considered as stress-free at 900°C and cooled to room temperature followed by a temperature cycle 20 → 600 → 20°C. In the first cooling of the composite, which simulates the fabrication process, the matrix undergoes large plastic deformations. The following temperature cycle results in a hysteresis loop, including both elastic and plastic deformations, with a total strain-range of $\Delta\epsilon = 0.0077$ m/m. Note that the matrix deformations occur at a

Fig. 7. Effective stress-strain relation in tungsten wire reinforced Hastelloy X. $V_f = 0.40$.

varying temperature.

The resistance to thermal fatigue for different matrices can be represented by the conventional Coffin-Manson's Equation as follows:

$$\Delta \epsilon = (3.5/E)(UTS)N_f^{-0.12} + D^{0.6}N_f^{-0.6} \quad (16)$$

where $D = \ln 1/(1-\Psi)$; Ψ = area reduction at fracture; $\Delta \epsilon$ total strain range; UTS = ultimate tensile strength; E = Young's modulus; N_f = cycles to failure.

The crack initiation and propagation in a composite matrix are not the same as in a monolithic material and the physical and mechanical properties may have been changed by the combination with the fibers. Present approach must therefore be used with care for the analysis of thermal fatigue problems in composites.

Strain-ranges for four composite systems subjected to temperature cycling were calculated by the present analyse method. The systems considered were tungsten wire reinforced stainless steel type 304, Kovar, Inconel 718 and Hastelloy X. Two types of temperature cycles were used: $20 \rightarrow 600 \rightarrow 20^\circ\text{C}$ and $20 \rightarrow 900 \rightarrow 20^\circ\text{C}$. For each composite system the fiber content was varied between 20 and 60 vol-% wires. However, it must be pointed out that the consideration of Inconel 718 is hypothetical while the material properties changes dramatically above the ageing temperature.

The estimated strain ranges were compared to the material properties calculated by Eq. (16). In Fig. 8 gives an example of the fatigue curves at 20 and 649°C for Hastelloy X. Indicated in the figure are also the predicted fatigue life for the two temperature cycles. Presently there is no method available for computing thermal fatigue life for a widely varying temperature history. In the present study a method used in ref [10] was introduced to estimate the number of cycles to failure for the $20 \rightarrow 600 \rightarrow 20$ cycle:

$$N_f = 2N_f(649)N_f(20) / [N_f(649) + N_f(20)] \quad (17)$$

Because of lack of reliable material properties at 900°C for the matrices used the fatigue life for the $20 \rightarrow 900 \rightarrow 20$ cycle were estimated based on the data at 649°C .

The number of cycles to failure predicted in this way are shown in Fig. 9. Thus the $\Delta \epsilon$ - N_f curves were estimated by Eq. (16) based on data from the material suppliers. The influence of creep was not included and no corrections were made for changes of the material properties during composite fabrication.

Fig. 8. Thermal fatigue life of of the Hastelloy X matrix reinforced by 40 vol % tungsten wires.

Fig. 9. Thermal fatigue life in composites with potential matrix materials.

For all the composite systems, N_f was estimated to be in the region 1000 - 5000 for temperature cycling between 20 and 900°C while the composites show a more scattered fatigue life for temperature cycles between 20 and 600°C. The difference in thermal expansion coefficients between the wires and the matrix is the most important parameter with respect to thermal fatigue. Stainless steel and superalloys have about the same coefficients while Kovar has a very low coefficient below, say 600°C. The mechanical properties of the matrix materials influence both the

deformations and the fatigue tolerance. A low tensile stress gives high plastic deformations in the matrix. But the total strain range, $\Delta\epsilon$, is mainly dependent on the temperature cycle ΔT and the difference in thermal expansion, $\Delta\alpha$. It is therefore essentially the internal stress level in the composite that is influenced by the matrix tensile stress. In matrices with high tensile stress most of the deformations, caused by thermal cycling, are elastic and the elastic constants have some importance. Eq. (16) shows that UTS and fracture ductility, Ψ , have influence on N_f . A high UTS imply a good resistance to small $\Delta\epsilon$ preferentially in the elastic region while a high ductility, Ψ , is more important to the fatigue life for cycles including large strain amplitudes where plastic deformations are dominating.

Among the matrices considered, Kovar shows a superior fatigue life for the 20 \rightarrow 600 \rightarrow 20 cycle. This is due to the small differences in thermal expansion coefficients between tungsten and Kovar in this temperature region. However, when this composite is subjected to thermal cycling between 20 and 900°C, the strain range is enough to give a rather low N_f . The main difference between Inconel 718 and Hastelloy X is that the former is age hardening and has a higher UTS compared to Hastelloy X. This is the primary reason why Inconel 718 has a superior N_f for the 20 \rightarrow 600 \rightarrow 20°C cycle compared to Hastelloy X. It is, however, probable that the UTS for Inconel 718 is considerably reduced during the composite fabrication which occurs above the solution temperature. Composites with a stainless steel matrix have poor thermal fatigue life due to the moderate mechanical properties. When the composites are subjected to the higher temperature cycle there are only small differences in N_f for the matrices analysed here. The potential application of this type of composites is at very high temperatures why the problems with thermal fatigue have to be seriously considered.

Tungsten wire reinforced FeCrAlY has been reported to have satisfactory thermal fatigue resistance [11]. This can, at least to some extent, be explained by the somewhat lower expansion coefficient, compared to superalloys and a very high ductility at elevated temperatures.

Preliminary thermal cycling tests of W-Kovar and W-SS composites indicate that the present theoretical analysis gives an adequate estimation of the fatigue problems. The test program will continue and also include Inconel 718 and Hastelloy X reinforced by tungsten wires.

STRESSES IN REACTION LAYERS

In systems of metallic fibers and metallic matrix, boundary layers of usually brittle intermetallic phases are observed. The brittle reaction layers may give rise to microcracks, diminishing the composite strength. It is therefore essential to analyse the stresses in the interaction zone.

In the tungsten wire reinforced stainless steel a brittle reaction layer, with the approximate composition (in weight %) 55 W, 33 Fe, 9 Cr, 3 Ni, was formed. Fig. 10. The growth of the layer was parabolic and controlled by a diffusion process. Due to the time and temperature involved in the composite fabrication, layers with thicknesses up to $20 \cdot 10^{-6}$ m were observed in this system.

Residual stresses in composites containing such reaction layers were predicted. Fiber and matrix data described previously were used. Some of the mechanical and physical properties for the reaction material were obtained from tests of a powder material, with the same composition. The thermal expansion coefficients were measured by dilatometer tests and taken to be 10, 12 and $15 \cdot 10^{-6}$ °C⁻¹ at 20, 500 and 900°C respectively. Young's modulus at room temperature was obtained from compressive tests to $229 \cdot 10^3$ [MPa]. It was assumed to decrease linearly to $185 \cdot 10^3$ at 900°C. The reaction layer was assumed to be deformed elastically, without plastic deformations.

The calculated residual microstresses in a composite, containing 40 vol-% wires and reaction layers with varying thicknesses, are presented in Fig. 11. The composite was assumed stress-free at 900°C and cooled to room temperature. The axial and

Fig. 10. Section through wire in a composite showing interfacial reaction layer after heat treatment (71 h at 1150°C).

Fig. 11. Predicted residual stresses in the reaction layer in a tungsten/stainless steel system.

tangential stress components in the reaction layer are on a very high tensile level. In comparison, the radial component is compressive and small. The effect of a varying layer thickness is negligible.

The predicted large stresses in the reaction layer can be explained by the absence of plastic deformations. Since, this material is brittle the stresses are of such a magnitude that cracks may be anticipated. Examination of the interaction zone, in the composite considered, shows cracks parallel to the fibers, Fig. 12. The wires are anisotropic and contain very long grains oriented in the wire direction. This

Fig. 12. Cracks along the wire in a reaction layer.

fact may explain why cracks appear only as a result of the tangential stress component despite the axial component is in the same order of magnitude.

AXIAL LOADING OF COMPOSITES

Composites subjected to loading parallel to the fibers have been analyzed by the present program. Effects of a previous heat treatment on the composite stress-strain relation were investigated.

Typical oriented fiber-metal matrix composites exhibit three distinctly different, but contiguous, types of strain response to an increasing tensile loading. On the initial application of tensile load, both matrix and fiber respond completely elastically (Stage I). After the elastic limit of the weaker components has been exceeded, one component responds with plastic strain, while the other continues to respond elastically (Stage II). Finally both components respond with plastic strains to continued tensile loading (Stage III).

The previous analysis of thermal microstresses in the composite system considered has shown that the stresses are of such magnitude that the matrix often is in a plastic state. Because of these residual stresses in actual composites, realization of Stage I performance to any significant extent is seldom achieved. Therefore, the performance characteristics is normally limited to Stage II and Stage III. The axial stress-strain curve, at room temperature, for tungsten wire reinforced Kovar was predicted by the present method and compared to an experimental curve, Fig. 13. The composite contains 27 vol-% wires. The matrix was estimated to be in a tensile plastic state, after composite fabrication. Hence, the composite responds with Stage II performance when an axial load was applied. After only a small strain the elastic limit of the tungsten wires was reached and both the fibers and matrix responds plastically. The calculation of the composite stress-strain relation was based on component data for uncombined material. Interaction during composite fabrication results in some reduction of mechanical properties. This fact may, to some extent explain why the experimental curve fall slightly below the predicted.

Tungsten wires embedded in a stainless steel matrix are brittle at room temperature. It is therefore suitable to analyse the stress-strain relation for this system at a temperature, where the wires are ductile. In Fig. 14 the predicted curve is compared to the experimental one for this composite system. The composite contains 35 vol-% wires and was tested at 300°C.

Fig. 13. Experimental and theoretical predicted stress-strain curves for tungsten wire reinforced Kovar at room temperature.

Fig. 14. Experimental and theoretical predicted stress-strain curves for tungsten wire reinforced stainless steel at 300°C.

Before the axial load was applied the composite was subjected to cooling after composite fabrication followed by increasing the temperature to 300°C. The matrix was, in this case, estimated to be in a compressive elastic state. Therefore the composite demonstrated all three stages of deformations when it was subjected to the axial loading. The difference between theoretical and experimental curves may partly be due to changes in material properties during composite fabrication and partly to uncertainty in the estimation of residual stresses.

CONCLUSIONS

It has been shown here that the microstresses in fiber reinforced metals can be analysed adequately by the cylindrical composite simulation model. Tungsten wire reinforced metals subjected to thermal cycling were analysed. Thermal fatigue was identified as a serious problem in potential composite systems. Microstresses in reaction layers were predicted. Cracks in the reaction zone were discussed in relation to appearing microstresses.

Finally, the stress-strain curves for composites were predicted and compared to tensile tests. Due to residual stresses the composites, subjected to axial loading, respond by stage II and III deformations in most cases.

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